

Role of chemically modified guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid [GABA] resin for removal of toxic metal ions from industrial wastewater

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Abstract : A new guar gum based guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid [GABA] resin has been synthesized and their adsorption behavior for toxic metal ions has been investigated by batch and column experiments. An application was undertaken regarding the adsorption of different toxic metal ions from effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Jodhpur using GABA resin. The distribution coefficient value of metal ions at different pH was also studied using batch equilibration method. The different factors affecting metal ion adsorption on this substrate such as pH, treatment time, agitation speed, flow rate and temperature were studied in detail. The prepared GABA resin was characterized by FTIR, ion exchange capacity (IEC), elemental and thermogravimetric analysis. The durability and swelling studies of GABA resin were also studied. The adsorption of different metal ions on GABA resin follows the order : $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{Fe}^{2+} > \text{Pb}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$.

Keywords : Distribution coefficients, IEC, GABA resin, ion exchangers, toxic metal ions.

Introduction

The pollution of the environment with toxic metals is a result of many human activities, such as mining and metallurgy, and the effects of these metals on the ecosystems are of large economic and public-health significance. In view of this, the need of developing viable and relevant technologies that can not only cleanup but also recover valuable components from industrial effluent and wastewater.

Different methods such as precipitation¹, solvent extraction^{2,3}, chemical and electrochemical technique⁴, advanced oxidation process^{5,6}, ion-exchange method⁷⁻¹¹, ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis^{12,13} have been developed for the removal of toxic metal ions from industrial effluents and wastewater¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

Ion-exchangers of polyvalent metals often exhibit much better ion-exchange behavior and are always of interest because of their higher selectivity, resistance to higher temperature, radiation field and to some extent chemical stability than those of commercial ion-exchange resins. The ion exchange capacity of these resins depends mainly on quantity of functional groups and pH of solution. The most widespread chelating functional groups are : thio,

thiourea, dithizone and triisobutyl phosphine sulfide which are used for removal of toxic metal ions from effluent and slow adsorption kinetics is their undesired characteristics. Inorganic ion-exchange materials also have been established to have applications in various disciplines, i.e. environmental studies, medical science (kidney dialysis), ion-selective electrode preparation, heterogeneous solid-state membrane formation, preconcentration and ion-exchange fibers preparation. Inorganic-organic materials are known to have a large selectivity for mono- and multivalent cations¹⁷.

The increasing number of publications on adsorption of toxic compounds by modified polysaccharides shows that there is a recent increasing interest in the synthesis of new low-cost adsorbents used in wastewater treatment¹⁸. The recent developments in the synthesis of adsorbents containing polysaccharides, in particular modified biopolymers derived from chitin¹⁹, chitosan²⁰, starch²¹, cellulose²² and cyclodextrin²³, which are not only eco-friendly and cost-effective but are effective also in remediation of common effluents present in the wastewater.

Guar gum is a galactomannan biopolymeric material isolated from the endosperms of *Cyamopsis tetragonalobus*,

which is native to northwestern parts of India²⁴. A polysaccharide consisting of linear chains of mannose with $1\beta\rightarrow4$ linkages to which galactose units are attached with $1\alpha\rightarrow6$ linkages. The ratio of mannose to galactose is 2 : 1. The structure of guar gum is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structure of guar gum.

The guar gum may be potentially used as an adsorbent; however, its water solubility does not permit this under aqueous condition. Its stability²⁵ and solubility as well as its sorption capacity can be altered through functionalisation by organic group²⁶ and chelating agent²⁷. Chuan *et al.*²⁸ studied the synthesis and characterization of novel guar gum hydrogels and their use as Cu^{II} sorbent. A hydrophilic polysaccharide matrix of guaran has been used for the preparation of some new chelating resins, i.e. glycine hydroxamate in guaran (GH-G), acetic acid hydroxamate in guaran (AAH-G) and iminodiacetic acid dihydroxamate in guaran (IDAAH-G) after its crosslinking with epichlorohydrin²⁹.

The ion exchangers based on guar gum powder are hydrophilic and biodegradable, whereas other ion exchangers have been prepared from petrochemical products which are not hydrophilic and biodegradable. Due to rising prices of petroleum products the guar gum powder has been selected for development of guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid [GABA] resin, which is very low cost, because it is locally available in large quantities from agriculture resources and these biopolymers are environment friendly.

In this work, we describe the synthesis and character-

ization of GABA resin and its application for removal and recovery of toxic metal ions from effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Jodhpur, India. For this purpose, various factors affecting the adsorption including pH, distribution coefficient (K_d), percentage removal of metal ion were studied.

Results and discussion

FT-IR characterization of guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid (GABA) resin :

Varian model 640 FT-IR instrument was employed for the FT-IR spectral analysis of guar gum, epoxypropylether of guar gum and synthesized GABA resin using KBr pellets.

The FT-IR spectrum of guar gum powder shows a broad band in the region $3600\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of -OH stretching. The peak at 2929 cm^{-1} is attributed to C-H stretching vibrations, a strong and sharp peak at 1650 cm^{-1} due to O-H bending and a variable peak at $1480\text{--}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to C-H bending. A strong peak at $1300\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ denotes C-O stretching vibration. The spectrum of guar gum is shown in Fig. 3.

The FT-IR spectrum of epoxypropylether of guar gum shows a strong peak in the region $1200\text{--}1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which represents symmetrical stretching or ring breathing frequency of the epoxy ring. The spectrum of epoxypropylether of guar gum is shown in Fig. 4.

The FT-IR spectrum of GABA resin shows a peak at 2950 cm^{-1} attributed to C-H stretching vibration. A strong peak in the region $1250\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ denotes C-O stretching vibrations. The C-N stretching band observed at $1200\text{--}1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$, a peak in the region $3500\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ denotes $>\text{NH}$ stretching vibration. The peak at $1700\text{--}1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to C=O stretching vibrations of aryl carboxylic acid. The peaks at $1620, 1602, 1499\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to C=C stretching in aromatic nuclei. The GABA resin in H^+ form shows the symmetric stretching vibration region $2500\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to -OH group in carboxylic acid. The GABA resin shows another variable peak at $1600\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to C-H bending. The spectrum of polysaccharides are generally observed in the region $3600\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to O-H

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectrum of epoxypropylether of guar gum.

stretching frequency³⁰. The IR spectrum of GABA resin is given in Fig. 5.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

Thermogravimetric analyzer model 951 was employed for this purpose. The polymer sample was powdered to the same average mesh size and dried carefully in vacuum desiccator. The boat was packed uniformly for analysis. For the dynamic measurement, the system was heated at

a constant heating rate of 20 °C per minute under static air atmosphere till the complete decomposition. The GABA resin is found to stable up to 398 °C and then the degradation was found to be rapid. There is a loss (approximately 7 wt. %) in the weight of GABA resin at 100 °C.

Elemental analysis :

Carlo Erba model 1160 elemental analyzer was used for determination of CHNO in the synthesized resin. The

Fig. 5. FT-IR spectrum of guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid [GABA] resin.

results of the elemental analysis are in good agreement with calculated value. Theoretically calculated (%) 48.41 (C); 6.05 (H); 41.49 (O) and 4.03 (N). Found (%) 48.04 (C); 5.85 (H); 40.95 (O) and 3.65 (N).

Ion exchange capacity (IEC) of GABA resin :

It was found to be 5.85 meq/g of the dry GABA resin. The ion exchange capacity of wet resin Amberlite IR-120 synthetic resin is 1.9 meq/ml studied by Demirbas *et al.*³¹. Total exchange capacity of IRN77 and SKN1 cation exchange resins are < 1.9 eq/L (H⁺ form) and < 1.7 meq/ml calculated by Rengaraj *et al.*³². Cation exchange resin Purolite C100 has exchange capacity 2.0 eq/L studied by Abo-Far *et al.*³³. Thus GABA resin is more suitable due to high ion exchange capacity.

Resin durability :

It was observed that the adsorbency of different metal ion on the GABA resin after 10 cycles (adsorption and desorption) and ion exchange capacities of reported resin were almost constant. The adsorbed metal ions were easily desorbed by treatment of different strength of acids, at room temperature. Table 2 shows the adsorbency of different metal ions on the GABA resin after 10 cycles (adsorption and desorption).

Table 1. The characteristic features of effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Basani, Jodhpur

Appearance :	Turbid						
Colour :	Green						
pH :	4.4						
Total hardness :	965 ppm						
Metal ion	Fe ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Pb ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺
Concentration (ppm)	1.19	1.02	8.28	1.82	1.18	10.20	70.0
Other anions (ppm) :	fluoride = 0.37; sulphate = 740.12; cyanide = 0.08.						

Table 2. The adsorption percentage of different metal ions on GABA resin (adsorption and desorption)

Metal ions	Adsorption percentage of different metal ions onto GABA resin after cycles				
	1 cycle	2 cycles	4 cycles	8 cycles	10 cycles
Cu ²⁺	96.08	94.86	92.10	91.89	91.98
Cd ²⁺	95.07	93.51	92.00	92.71	92.45
Fe ²⁺	94.65	92.40	91.68	91.09	91.99
Pb ²⁺	93.00	92.89	91.52	91.22	91.15
Zn ²⁺	91.05	89.05	88.51	88.06	88.98

Distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions in effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Basani, Jodhpur :

The pH has a strong effect on the distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions. The results of distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions from effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Jodhpur are given in Table 3. The perusal of the results shows that the distribution coefficient value first increases and then decreases with increasing pH, the optimum results obtained at pH 5.0. Difference in distribution coefficient at the same pH for different metal ions suggests possible strategy for separation of these ions from their mixture. Metal sorption starts when the pH rises to the range where most acidic ion exchange sites start to exchange hydronium ion for metal and the capacity reaches the maximum value in the pH range where all the ion exchange sites take part in the reaction and the functional group is able to form complex with the metal cations³⁴.

Table 3. Distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions from effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Basani, Jodhpur on GABA resin (K_d) × 10²

pH	Fe ²⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cu ²⁺
1	0.87	15.63	11.16	13.09	11.63
2	2.40	25.27	19.38	24.53	32.28
3	4.99	29.49	42.85	31.19	51.99
4	14.64	49.04	74.09	48.89	67.71
5	134.50	86.49	137.28	65.70	172.05
6	3.09	14.46	7.30	5.63	3.84

Removal of metal ions from effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Basani, Jodhpur by GABA resin :

The result of percentage removal of metal ions from effluent of Puneet Steel Industry by GABA resin is given in Table 4. It is clear from the reported Table that the percentage removal of metal ions are directly propor-

Table 4. Removal percentage of metal ions from effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Basani, Jodhpur on GABA resin

pH	Fe ²⁺	Pb ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cu ²⁺
1	11.07	69.20	61.37	65.46	62.00
2	25.44	78.02	73.57	78.06	81.94
3	41.27	80.53	85.77	82.20	88.01
4	68.00	87.73	91.53	87.44	90.51
5	94.65	93.00	95.07	91.05	96.08
6	30.25	67.23	51.09	44.67	35.11

tional to the K_d values of metal ions and the optimum results obtained at pH 5.0. It has been found that the maximum percentage removal of Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Zn^{2+} are 96.08, 95.07, 94.65, 93.00 and 91.05%, respectively. The relative standard deviation values (RSD) of optimum removal percentage of metal ions are shown in Table 5. All data represent the mean of three independent experiments.

Table 5. Optimum results for the removal of metal ions from the effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Jodhpur on GABA resin at pH 5.0

Metal ions	Amount of metal ions in effluent (mg)	Amount loaded on GABA resin (mg)	Removal percentage	RSD (%) ^a
Fe^{2+}	1.19	1.12	94.65	1.37
Cd^{2+}	1.82	1.73	95.07	0.80
Zn^{2+}	1.02	0.92	91.05	1.36
Pb^{2+}	1.18	1.09	93.00	1.87
Cu^{2+}	8.28	7.95	96.08	1.73

^aMean of three replicate determinations.

Recovery of metal ions :

The metal ions were eluted quantitatively with different strength of acids. Cu^{2+} was eluted with 2.5 N HCl; Cd^{2+} with 2.0 N HCl; Fe^{2+} with 1.5 N HCl; Zn^{2+} with 0.5 N HCl and Pb^{2+} was eluted with 1 N HCl. Then the resin column was washed thoroughly with demineralized water. Thus Cu^{2+} was eluted by the higher concentration of hydrochloric acid, then the lower concentration of hydrochloric acid was used to elute Zn^{2+} because the affinity between Cu^{2+} and cation resin is larger than that of Zn^{2+} . These results are reported in Table 6. Dev and Rao modified Amberlite XAD-4 with bis-(*N,N*-salicylidene)-1,3-propanediamine for the separation of Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and sorbed

Table 6. Quantitative separation of metal ions on GABA column

Metal ions	Amount loaded (mg)	Amount found (mg)	Recovery (%)	Eluent use	Eluent volume (ml)
Zn^{2+}	0.92	0.88	95.81	0.5 N HCl	52
Pb^{2+}	1.09	1.06	97.86	1.0 N HCl	46
Fe^{2+}	1.12	1.09	98.08	1.5 N HCl	51
Cd^{2+}	1.73	1.70	98.38	2.0 N HCl	56
Cu^{2+}	7.95	7.87	99.01	2.5 N HCl	44

metals were eluted by 1 M HCl with a recovery of 97–100%³⁵.

Moisture contents :

A physical property of the ion exchange resins with changes in cross linkage is the moisture content of the resin. The amount of cross linking depends on the proportions of different monomers used in the polymerization step. So it is important to determine the moisture contents of the synthesized resins. One gram of the resin in hydrogen form was taken and dried to a constant weight in vacuum desiccator at 85 °C overnight and the resin was weighed. Moisture percentage = 7%.

Effect of pH :

GABA resin forms complexes with various metal ions at specific pH conditions. The pH is an important parameter for adsorption of metal ions from aqueous solution because it affects the solubility of the metal ions, concentration of the counter ions on the functional groups of the adsorbent and the degree of ionization of the adsorbent during reaction. To examine the adsorption percentage of metal ions with pH, the pH was varied from 1.0 to 6.0. Adsorption of metal ions on GABA resin increased over pH range from 1.0 to 5.0 and optimum adsorption of metal ions occurs at pH 5 and then declining at higher pH. These results are reported in Table 4. After pH 7.0, the insoluble metal ions starts precipitating from the solution, making true sorption studies impossible. pH influences the equilibrium of metal ion uptake in aqueous solution by affecting the speciation of metal ions in solution, the concentration of the competing hydrogen ions as well as the chemistry of the active binding sites on the sorbent³⁶.

Effect of agitation speed :

The effect of agitation speed on adsorption of metal ions was studied by varying the speed of agitation from 0 (without shaking) to 140 rpm, while keeping the optimum temperature (25 °C) and optimum pH as constant. It is clear from Fig. 6 that the adsorption of metal ions on GABA resin increased when agitation speed increased from 0 to 120 rpm. These results can be associated to the fact that the increase of the agitation speed, improves the diffusion of metal ions towards the surface of the adsorbents. This also indicates that a shaking rate in the range 120–140 rpm is sufficient to assure that all the

Fig. 6. Effect of agitation speed on adsorption of metal ions on GABA resin.

surface binding sites are made readily available for metal ions uptake. Then, the effect of external film diffusion on adsorption rate can be assumed not significant. For convenience, agitation speed of 130 rpm was selected as the optimum speed for GABA resin for removal of metal ions from effluent of Puneet Steel Industry. These results are in close agreement with the reports by Jeon and Park³⁷.

Effect of treatment time :

Treatment time indicate that adsorption percentage of metal ions increased with an increase in contact time before equilibrium is reached. It is clear from Fig. 7 that adsorption of metal ions on GABA resin increased when

Fig. 7. Effect of changing treatment time on the adsorption percentage of different metal ions on GABA resin.

contact time was increased from 30 to 210 min, optimum contact time for GABA adsorbent was found to be 210 min. Other parameters such as pH of solution and agitation speed were kept optimum, while temperature was kept at 25 °C. Greater availability of carboxylic and amine functional groups on the surface of guar gum powder which are required for interaction with metal ions, significantly improved the binding capacity and the process proceeded rapidly. This result is important, as equilibrium time is one of the important parameters for an economical wastewater treatment system.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Guar gum powder (Ases Chemical Works, Jodhpur, India), epichlorohydrin (Aldrich, USA), 4-aminobenzoic acid (Loba Chemic Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India), sodium hydroxide (Sarabhai M. Chemicals, Baroda, India), dioxane (E. Merck, Mumbai, India) were used as supplied.

Sample :

The effluent of Puneet Steel Industry, Basani, Jodhpur (Rajasthan) has following characteristic features as given in Table 1.

Synthesis of guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid (GABA) resin :

Synthesis of guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid resin was accomplished in the following two steps, A and B.

(A) Preparation of epoxy propyl ether of tamarind :

An amount of 162 g of guar gum powder (1 mol) was taken in a round bottom flask and it was slurred with 65 ml of dioxane. 15 ml of 40% (w/v) sodium hydroxide was added to make alkaline, till pH reached 9.5. The solution was stirred for 2 h at 60 °C. 9.25 g epichlorohydrin (0.1 mol) was added with constant stirring. The stirring was further continued for 5 h, at 60 °C. The product epoxy-propyl ether of guar gum powder was filtered under vacuum and washed with methanol to remove impurities and dried.

(B) Preparation of guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid (GABA) resin :

Epoxypropyl ether of guar gum was then allowed to react with 13.71 g (0.1 mol) of 4-aminobenzoic acid and the stirring was continued for another 4 h at 60 °C. The

product so formed was filtered under vacuum and washed with methanol and dried. The yield of guar gum 4-aminobenzoic acid resin is 194.74 g and degree of substitution (DS) is 0.10. The reaction scheme is shown in Fig. 2.

Column experiment :

In the column experiment, a glass tube with 1.6 cm internal diameter and 20 cm height, packed with 10 cm of resin (9.4 g) was used. 50 ml of the reference metal ion solution were passed through the column at a flow rate of 2 ml per minute. The flow rate was controlled by a peristaltic pump. The column was washed with 20 ml of deionized water and the washing was rejected. The metal ions were eluted quantitatively with different strength of acids.

Determination of distribution coefficient :

The distribution coefficient (K_d) of metal ions on resins were determined by batch method at 25 °C. In all cases for the determination of K_d , a 50 ml reference solution was taken in a conical flask and the pH was adjusted by acetic acid + sodium acetate and ammonium hydroxide + ammonium chloride. 70 mg of GABA resin were added to the solution and stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 2 h and the contents were equilibrated. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 40. The residue on the filter paper was equilibrated with 25 ml of 4 N HCl, and the solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42.

The toxic metal ion concentrations in the filtrate as well as in the residue were estimated using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). The calibration curves for different metal ions were plotted, by analyzing a series of standard solutions of metal ions using AAS. The different wavelengths of main resonance line and air acetylene flame were used for the determination of various metals. The concentration of metal ion in filtrate was determined by the calibration curves. The distribution coefficient (K_d) on GABA resin was calculated using the following formula³⁸ :

$$K_d = \frac{\text{Amount of metal ion in resin phase}}{\text{Amount of metal ion in solution phase}} \times \frac{\text{Volume of solution (ml)}}{\text{Weight of dry resin (g)}}$$

Determination of percentage removal of metal ions concentration :

The initial metal ion concentration in solution and filtrate after equilibrium with resin were estimated using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The percentage removal of metal ions was calculated using this formula.

$$\text{Percentage removal of metal ions} = [(I - F/I) \times 100]$$

where I is the initial amount of the metal ion in solution, F is the final amount of metal ion in solution after equilibrium with resin.

Determination of ion exchange capacity (IEC) of GABA :

Resin capacity is usually expressed in terms of equivalents per liter (eq/L) of resin or mill equivalents per dry gram of resin. The ion exchange capacity, which is generally taken as a measure of the hydrogen ion liberated by neutral salt to flow through the composite cation exchanger was determined by standard column process. An amount of 10 g (dry mass) of the composite ion exchange material in H^+ form was placed in a glass column with a glass wool support at the bottom. It was washed with demineralized water to remove any excess of acid remained on the particles. The hydrogen ions eluted with 0.1 M solution of different alkali and alkaline earth salts. The flow rate was kept 4 ml min^{-1} . The collected effluent was titrated against a standard solution of sodium hydroxide using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The hydrogen ions released were then calculated.

Conclusion :

The adsorption behavior of GABA resin towards Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} ions from aqueous solution were investigated under different conditions including agitation speed, pH, treatment time and temperature. It was found that, the GABA resin is effective adsorbent (almost 96%) for the removal of different toxic metal ions from effluent of Steel Industry, Jodhpur, India follows the order : $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{Fe}^{2+} > \text{Pb}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$. The adsorption-desorption studies showed that the resin were reusable without a significant decrease in the ion adsorption capacities. The process is very efficient especially in case of low concentrations of pollutants in aqueous solutions, where common methods are either economically unfavorable or technically complicated.

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